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Review Article

**A REVIEW ON THE SARS-COV-2 PANDEMIC SITUATION
AND RESPONSE IN PAKISTAN****Asad Khan¹, Abdullah², Muhammad Aamir Shehzad¹, Arif Khan¹, Bakhtiar Ali²,
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Pakistan³Department of life sciences, Shandong Normal University, China**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

In late December 2019, a coronavirus disease called COVID-19 caused by SARS-CoV-2 was originated from China and spread vigorously in more than 200 countries worldwide including Pakistan and Iran. Being the neighbor country of China and Iran, Pakistan was more vulnerable to COVID-19. With the report of very first case in Pakistan, even with less resources, Pakistan reacted toward the pandemic by arranging special hospitals, diagnostics centers, quarantine facilities, awareness campaigns and lockup to prevent virus spread. Pakistan also announce immediate closer of all schools, colleges and universities along with partial lockdown in all the major cities. The current review highlights Pakistani situation and response to control COVID-19.

Key Words: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, Pakistan, situation

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INTRODUCTION:

The emergence of infectious diseases, including SARS (severe acute respiratory syndrome), MERS (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome) and other viruses present significant challenge to public health [1–3]. In late December 2019, an outbreak occurred of indescribable pneumonia in china, Hubei province, Wuhan [4]. On January 7, 2020, it was confirmed that a new type of coronavirus called SARS-CoV-2 (formerly known as 2019-nCoV) had appeared [5]. On February 11, 2020, WHO (World Health Organization) named the Wuhan pneumonia as COVID-19 (Coronavirus Disease-2019) [6]. The patient's COVID-19 displayed distinctive respiratory symptoms such as dry cough, fever, myalgia (lung damage) and some other signs like aches and pains, nasal congestion, runny nose and diarrhea [7,8]. Coronaviruses are RNA viruses (enveloped) that are widely distributed among mammals, humans, mammals, and birds and cause respiratory enteric (infection in small intestines), liver failure (hepatic), and neurologic diseases in the respiratory system [9,10]. SARS-CoV-2 genome sequences shared a 79.5 percent sequence identity with SARSCo-V (severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronaviruses) [11, 12]. Six common human coronavirus species are known to cause human disease [13]. Four viruses 229E (alpha coronavirus), OC43 (beta coronavirus), NL63 (alpha coronavirus), and HKU1 (beta coronavirus) are prevalent and usually infect immune-competent individuals with common cold symptoms [13]. The other two strains SARS-CoV (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus) and MERS-CoV (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus) are zoonotic by origin and have often been related to fatal disease [14]. As of 17 April 2020 a total of 2, 074,529 Confirmed cases were recorded in more than 213 countries with 139,378 death tools according to WHO reports (<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019>).

In Pakistan coronavirus positive cases were reported on 26, February 2020, the pilgrims returned from Iran after attending religious congregation. Subsequently, the COVID-19 spread all over the country and until now 7,993 cases are confirmed with 159, death tolls [16]. This study was aimed to highlight the COVID-19 scenario in Pakistan.

Current status of COVID-19 in Pakistan:

Pakistan has experienced several viral outbreaks including recent SARS-CoV-2 outbreak [25-27]. On Wednesday, June 17, 2020, a total of 154, 737 confirmed positive cases along with 2,975 deaths were recorded according to the national disaster management authority (NDMA), government of Pakistan. The highest positive cases were reported in Punjab province (58,239), followed by Sindh

(57,868), Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (19,107), Baluchistan (8,437), Gilgit Baltistan (1,164), Islamabad (9,242) and Azad Jammu & Kashmir with 703 cases as summarized in table 01 [16].

Table1. Current situation of COVID-19 in Pakistan

Provinces	Confirmed cases	Active cases	Death	Recoveries
AJK	703	400	13	290
Baluchistan	8,437	5,325	89	3,023
GB	1,164	409	17	738
Islamabad	9,242	6,713	90	24,39
KPK	19,107	13,454	731	4,922
Punjab	58,239	39,310	1,149	17,780
Sindh	57,868	27,737	886	29,245

Facilitation by Government of Pakistan against COVID-19:

The government of Pakistan is taking all the possible steps to control COVID-19 and provide and ensure better health of the citizen. Since the 1st case confirmation in Karachi, all the possible options were availed to minimize the transmission of the disease and protect public health in the area. Initial investigation revealed that the COVID-19 positive cases have a travel history to affected countries and therefore the disease entrance in to Pakistan can be linked to international travels. The government of Pakistan is offering several steps such as early case detection and contact monitoring, risk communication, enforcing social distance, quarantine and isolation facilitation to prevent COVID-19 from further spreading (17). The government has also set up a COVID-19 Relief Fund to collect donations for public welfare and to facilitate daily wages and has launched a social network helpline in seven (07) local languages. In all tertiary care hospitals, district headquarters hospitals and private clinics throughout the province, the provincial and local governments released guidelines on the closure of OPDs and elective surgical facilities from 1-13 April 2020. The Central Emergency Relief Fund (CERF) has allocated \$60 million for COVID-19 to global response program. The Sindh Government built its first COVID-19 test facility center in Karachi [18].

Hospitals for COVID-19 in Pakistan:

Several steps are being taken by the government of Pakistan to monitor the outbreak and to facilitate its citizens. In this situation, there have been many hospitals working to bring back life and fight against the deadly COVID-19 epidemic in the country. There is a functional hospital in the capital territory Islamabad, 10 hospitals in Baluchistan. 07 hospitals in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, 06 in Punjab, 04 in Sindh and 04 in Gilgit-Baltistan, and 03 in Azad Jammu and Kashmir. (19) as shown in the fig.1

Figure No. 1 Number of Hospitals for COVID-19 in Pakistan

Designated Hospitals:

Different hospitals have been approved for admission and management of suspected and confirmed based on the availability of federal, provincial and local standard isolation wards. Each institute and hospital are required to perform supply needs and availability assessments (equipment, personal protective equipment (PPE), laboratory diagnostics) including source identification to ensure the quality and availability of PPE and to notify and train IPC (Infection prevention and control) team at the specified hospitals. A qualified IPC focal person will be assigned to ensure embedded and imbedded IPC interventions. Distribution and application of the recently adopted National IPC Guidelines / SOPs (Standard Operational Procedure) which are following.

1. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) have been developed and disseminated for waste management at hospitals and airports. Local SOPs should be established and available in all HCFs with appropriate training of the staff assigned to handle the waste.

2. Disinfection and Environmental decontamination SOPs were developed.

Isolation wards were developed in Pakistan to prepare for COVID-19 pandemic, Province/region

wise number of designated hospitals are; ICT-01, Punjab-06, Sindh-04, Baluchistan-10, KP-07, GB-04 and AJK-03. The total number of beds in the countrywide isolation wards is 23,557. In the capital territory of Islamabad 350 beds were established, Punjab 10,948, Sindh 2,100, Baluchistan 5,897, KP 2,760, GB 972 and in AJK 530 bed facilities in insolation wards. (20)

Hospitals with isolation wards:

Isolation is distinct from quarantine and eradicates sick or infected individuals from others to avoid disease from spreading. The distributions of hospitals being used for isolation on districts basis are: one in Islamabad which was used for isolation with a capacity of 10 beds, each in districts of Baluchistan province (14) with medical facilities against COVID-19, 110 in province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, 50 in 34 districts of Punjab province with working medical facilities. Four medical facilities were available in the Sindh province, in the four districts. There are 21 medical facilities in the Gilgit-Baltistan districts, while 15 in the Azad Jammu and 9 in the Kashmir districts (21). as shown in fig No.2

Figure 2. Hospitals with isolation wards Province-wise for COVID-19 in Pakistan

Quarantine facilities:

The quarantines are used to limit the activities or separation of individuals who have not yet become ill, but who may have been exposed to an infectious agent or disease such as COVID 19 to track symptoms and detect cases early. There were 10 quarantine centers in Baluchistan, 52 in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, 06 in Punjab, 02 in Sindh , while 63 quarantine facilities were available for Gilgit-Baltistan. In AJK, four quarantine facilities were functional in the various districts (22).

Figure 3 Quarantine Facilities Province-wise for COVID-19 in Pakistan

Testing Facilities in Pakistan:

Internationally, RT-PCR is used as the safest and easiest approach for COVID-19 research, so Pakistan government also recommends the PCR technique. Across the various cities in Pakistan there are 15 developed diagnostic units distributed as; Islamabad 01, Balochistan 01, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 01, Punjab 04, Sindh 05, AJK 01, Gilgit Baldistan-01 and NIH mobile Diagnostic unit Taftan. These laboratories are well suited for COVID-19 diagnosis

with free PCR system (RT-PCR). Pakistan's research capacity has been developed from 30,000 to 280,000, which will be further expanded to 900,000. The country has effectively carried out 15,000 Coronavirus studies since the outbreak. The National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) works with the National Institute of Health (NIH) to raise the overall number of coronavirus research diagnostic laboratories from 15 to 50, in order to boost the research quality. The new research

laboratories set up will be planted across the different cities in Pakistan. Pakistan is also implementing a training program for paramedics and laboratory personnel to resolve the shortcoming. NDMA will hire 100 molecular biology- expert laboratory technicians (23).

CONCLUSION:

The COVID-19 went along by SARS-CoV-2 in China's Wuhan City, which spread quickly across the globe. In Pakistan, the cases of COVID-19 are increasing rapidly alarming the authorities to do more and to take some more steps with more facilitation. Pakistan is emergent country with have not better final position as compare to USA, Germany, china, and Spain to fight against the current outbreak. The quantity of hospitals and quarantines should be more advanced with latest diagnostics and treatment facilities. The public should also follow the government guidelines to avoid social gathering, wearing protective equipment, and minimizing virus exposure chances. Importantly, on our airports, both the arrivals and the departures need more screening facilities so the COVID-19 can be controlled from further spreading.

REFERENCES:

1. Drosten, C., Günther, S., Preiser, W., Van Der Werf, S., Brodt, H. R., Becker, S., ... & Berger, A. (2003). Identification of a novel coronavirus in patients with severe acute respiratory syndrome. *New England journal of medicine*, 348(20), 1967-1976.
2. Haq, I., Ullah, R., Din, M., Ahmad, S., Anwar, F., Ali, M., & Khan, H. U. (2020). Unrecognized HIV infection in asymptomatic volunteer blood donors at district Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *New Microbes and New Infections*, 100685.
3. ABDULLAH, SHER ALI, MUHAMMAD SALMAN, MISBAHUD DIN, KACHKOL KHAN, MUNIB AHMAD, FAISAL HAYAT KHAN, and MUHAMMAD ARIF. "Dengue Outbreaks in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Pakistan in 2017: An Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response System (IDSRS)-Based Report." *Polish Journal of Microbiology* 68, no. 1 (2019): 115-119
4. Gralinski, L. E., & Menachery, V. D. (2020). Return of the Coronavirus: 2019-nCoV. *Viruses*, 12(2), 135.
5. Burki, T. K. (2020). Coronavirus in China. *The Lancet. Respiratory Medicine*, 8(3), 238.
6. World Health Organization. WHO Director-General's remarks at the media briefing on 2019-nCoV on 11 February 2020. <https://www.who.int/dg/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-2019-ncov-on-11-february-2020>.
7. Guan, W. J., Ni, Z. Y., Hu, Y., Liang, W. H., Ou, C. Q., He, J. X., ... & Du, B. (2020). Clinical characteristics of 2019 novel coronavirus infection in China. *MedRxiv*.
8. Huang, C., Wang, Y., Li, X., Ren, L., Zhao, J., Hu, Y., ... & Cheng, Z. (2020). Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China. *The Lancet*, 395(10223), 497-506.
9. Weiss, S. R., & Leibowitz, J. L. (2011). Coronavirus pathogenesis. In *Advances in virus research* (Vol. 81, pp. 85-164). Academic Press.
10. Zhu, N., Zhang, D., Wang, W., Li, X., Yang, B., Song, J., ... & Niu, P. (2020). A novel coronavirus from patients with pneumonia in China, 2019. *New England Journal of Medicine*.
11. Zhou, P., Yang, X. L., Wang, X. G., Hu, B., Zhang, L., Zhang, W., ... & Chen, H. D. (2020). A pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin. *Nature*, 579(7798), 270-273.
12. Wu, A., Peng, Y., Huang, B., Ding, X., Wang, X., Niu, P., ... & Sheng, J. (2020). Genome composition and divergence of the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) originating in China. *Cell host & microbe*.
13. Su, S., Wong, G., Shi, W., Liu, J., Lai, A. C., Zhou, J., ... & Gao, G. F. (2016). Epidemiology, genetic recombination, and pathogenesis of coronaviruses. *Trends in microbiology*, 24(6), 490-502.
14. Cui, J., Li, F., & Shi, Z. L. (2019). Origin and evolution of pathogenic coronaviruses. *Nature reviews Microbiology*, 17(3), 181-192.
15. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/situation-reports>
16. The Ministry of National Health Services, Regulation and Coordination <http://covid.gov.pk/stats/pakistan>. Accessed 18th April 2020
17. National Institute of Health (NIH) <https://www.nih.org.pk/novel-coronavirus-2019-ncov/>. Accessed 18th April 2020
18. Relief Web - Informing humanitarians worldwide <https://reliefweb.int/>. Accessed 18th April 19, 2020.
19. The Ministry of National Health Services, Regulation and Coordination <http://covid.gov.pk/facilities/List%20of%20COVID-19>. Accessed April 19, 2020.
20. The Ministry of National Health Services, Regulation and Coordination <http://covid.gov.pk/facilities/List-of-Designated-Hospitals-1.pdf>. Accessed April 19, 2020.
21. The Ministry of National Health Services, Regulation and Coordination

- <http://covid.gov.pk/facilities/List%20of%20Province>. Accessed 18th April 2020
22. The Ministry of National Health Services, Regulation and Coordination <http://covid.gov.pk/facilities/List%20of%20Province-wise%20COVID>
 23. The Ministry of National Health Services, Regulation and Coordination
 24. <http://covid.gov.pk/facilities/List%20of%20Province-wise%20COVID-19%20Testing%20Facilities%20Pakistan.pdf>. Accessed 18th April 2020.
 25. Sajid Ali, Nourin Mahmood, Jehan Zeb Afridi, Bashir Ahmad, Abdullah, Misbahud Din, Munib Ahmad, Faisal Hayat Khan, Fazal Jalil. Epidemics of dengue virus in the recent outbreak in 2017, in District Mardan, Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan. *Int. J. Biosci.* 12(3), 280-284, March 2018.
 26. Mudassir Khan, Fazal Jalil, Misbahud Din, Sajid Ali, Aziz Ahmad. Seroprevalence and Risk Factors of Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) in Tehsil Takht Bhai District Mardan, KPK, Pakistan. *Int. J. Biosci.* 12(5), 249-254, May 2018.
 27. Muhammad Ali et al., Increasing Burden of Hepatitis C in Population of District Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province Of Pakistan., *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2019; 06(08).